

Scheme 1

4-N-Chloroacetyl-5-carbethoxycytosine (2): A mixture of 5-carbethoxycytosine (0.1 mol) and chloroacetylchloride (0.15 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. On evaporation of the solvent, the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from benzene, (73%, 19.0 g), m.p. 241° (Found: N, 16.15. C₉H₁₀ClN₂O₄ requires: N, 16.21%).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	177	67
2.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	186	71
3.	3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	196	70
4.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	201	66
5.	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	192	68
6.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	207	60
7.	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	211	64
8.	5-CH ₃ -2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	195-96	43
9.	2-Cl-4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	201	60
10.	2-CH ₃ -4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	197	71
11.	2-Cl-4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	211	62
12.	2,5-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	164	62
13.	2,6-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	181	68
14.	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	159	63
15.	4-NH ₂ -SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	268d	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

1(H)-4-(N'-Arylaminoacetamido)-5-carbethoxypyrimidin-2-ones (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and appropriate aromatic amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30-40 ml) was refluxed for 3 h in the presence of K₂CO₃ (2-3 g). The contents were

then poured into cold water and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacological screening: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using cup-plate⁸ method. Representative compounds were screened for anti-tubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₈₇R₀) by the absolute concentration method⁴.

Results and Discussion

Antibacterial activity: Out of 15 compounds (3), 8 compounds (sl. nos. 1, 4, 5, 7-9, 12, 15) were found to be active against *S. aureus* and 7 compounds (sl. nos. 3, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13, 15) active against *E. coli*. Compounds having 4-methoxy, 2,6-dimethyl, 2,5-dichloro and 4-sulphonamido substitutions were found to be active against both the species (sl. nos. 4, 7, 12, 15) (Table 1).

Antitubercular activity: Out of 7 compounds (3) screened (sl. nos. 2, 4, 7, 10, 11, 13, 15; Table 1) none was found effective at lower concentration (35 µg ml⁻¹). But only compound sl. no. 13 having 4-methoxy substituent was found active at higher concentration (100 µg ml⁻¹).

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Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-IV. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some 2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazolo/thiadiazolo[3,2-a]-s-triazine-7-thiones

M. M. DUTTA**, B. N. GOSWAMI and J. C. S. KATAKY*

Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006

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MANY s-triazine derivatives have a wide variety of uses such as pesticidal, herbicidal, antifungal and antibacterial activities^{1,2}. On the other hand, the importance of 1,3,4-oxa/thiadiazole derivatives as biologically active compounds are

**Department of Chemistry, N. N. Saikia College, Titabar-785 630.

NOTES

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY** DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Antibacterial activities		
					B.c	E.c	B.m
5a	CH ₃	208	70	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	-	+	+
5b	C ₆ H ₅	200	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	-	-	+
5c	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	187	81	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	+	-	+
6a	CH ₃	290	83	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS ₂	-	+	+
6b	C ₆ H ₅	224	79	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS ₂	+	+	+
6c	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	192	82	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₄ N ₄ OS ₂	+	+	++
7a	CH ₃	198	71	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	++	+	++
7b	C ₆ H ₅	178	68	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	++	+	++
7c	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	172	72	C ₁₆ H ₈ Cl ₄ N ₄ OS	++	++	++
8a	CH ₃	261	75	C ₁₁ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ S ₂	+	++	++ +
8b	C ₆ H ₅	201	69	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₄ S ₂	++	++	++
8c	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	180	72	C ₁₆ H ₈ Cl ₄ N ₄ S ₂	+++	++	+++

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and N analyses.

**B.c = *B. cereus*, E.c = *E. coli*, B.m = *B. megaterium*; Zone of inhibition: (+) = 1-3 mm, (++) = 4-6 mm, (+++) = 7-9 mm, (++++) = 10-12 mm and (-) = on inhibition.

ethanol (95%, charcoal) to afford 4. The acidic filtrate on basification with ammonia gave a small amount of solid which was found to be identical with 4, (89%), m.p. 225° (lit.¹⁸); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 275 - 3 100 (NH₂) and 1 625 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (ppm) 6.3-6.8 (m, ArH) and 4.0 (bs, NH₂).

N-Acyl-N'-[5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxa]thiazol-2-yl]thioureas (5a-c, 6a-c): A mixture of ammonium thiocyanate (0.01 mol) and acid chloride (0.01 mol) in acetone (25 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. Compound 3 (0.01 mol) was then added to it and the reaction mixture was refluxed further for 2-3 h. It was then poured into excess water. The resulting solid (5a-c) was dried and recrystallised from ethanol-acetone (50:50, v/v); following the same procedure, 6a-c were prepared: 5a-c ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 325-3 320 (NH), 1 670-1 660 (C=O) and 1 100 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 7.3-7.8 (m, ArH) and 4.8 (-NH); for compounds 6a-c 3 330-3 320 (NH), 1 670-1 665 (C=O) and 1 060 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 7.4-8.0 (m, ArH).

5-Alkylaryl-2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxa]thiazolo-[3,2-a]-s-triazine-7-thiones (7a-c, 8a-c): A mixture of 5a-c (0.015 mol), phosphorus oxychloride (15 ml) and phosphorus pentachloride (0.015 mol) was refluxed for 3-4 h. The excess phosphorus oxychloride was then removed under reduced pressure and crushed ice added to it. The resulting solid (7a-c) was recrystallised from ethanol; the same procedure was adopted for conversion of thioureas 6a-c to 8a-c: ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 100-1 070 (C=S) and 1 030 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); δ 6.6-7.8 (m, ArH), 2.2 (s, 3H).

The characterisation data of the compounds were presented in Table 1.

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